

USAGE OF N-LIST E-RESOURCES OF THE SELECT DEGREE COLLEGES AFFILIATED TO PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH; A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract *This research paper explains the usage of the N-LIST E-resources among the student and faculty members of the various select Degree Colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. A questionnaire method was used as a tool for collection of data from the 32 select degree colleges in Punjab and Chandigarh. The total data was collected from the 466 out of 513 respondents. The total response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466 respondents, total 286 are users (faculty and student) respondents and 180 are non-users (faculty and student) respondents. The statistical test have been applied and the inferences have been drawn thereof.*

Keywords: *E-Books, E-Journals, Bibliographical Databases, N-LIST, INFLIBNET, Usage of E-Resources, Degree Colleges of Panjab University, Statistical Analysis, Consortia*

INTRODUCTION

With the advent of resource sharing, the Library Consortia have brought economy, efficiency and equality in information availability and its usage. Through Library Consortia, the gap between information resource-rich libraries and resource-deficient libraries is expected to be bridged. Although, there are many consortia in India like UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortia, INDEST Consortia, CSIR Consortia etc which have already gained the popularity in India. Yet, N-LIST is one of such consortia which helps to bridge this gap and provides access to the E-resources to its users.

N-LIST: AN INITIATIVE OF NMEICT

The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT) was launched on 3rd Feb, 2009. It initiated a project called “National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)”, popularly known as N-LIST which was formally launched by Shri Kapil Sibal, Union Minister for Human Resource Development, on 4th May, 2010. The N-LIST Project is being jointly executed by the (University Grants Commission- Information Network) UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, Indian Institute of Technology

(IIT) Delhi. The project provides the cross-subscription to e-resources subscribed by the two Consortia, i.e. subscription to INDEST-AICTE resources for universities and UGC-INFONET resources for technical institutions; and the access to selected e-resources to colleges.

The Faculty and the students from the colleges covered under section 12B/ 2F of UGC Act are eligible to access e-resources through the N-LIST project. These colleges are required to register themselves on the N-LIST Website. During the last three years, the collection has increased from 2,100 to 6,000 e-journals and from 51,000 to 1, 00,000 e-books (ref. 2 homepage), subscribed under the N-LIST Project.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Akinola (2009)¹ obtained the results from her study which revealed that majority of the respondents (35.4%) from the University of Ibadan sought information to update knowledge. It was also found that the respondents also sought information for writing of papers or books, reading, and for

¹ Akinola, S.F. (2009) Information Seeking Behaviour of Lecturers in Faculties of Education in Obafemi Awolowo University, Heilfe and University of Ibadan. *Samaru Journal of Information Studies*. 9, 2:30.

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preparing class lectures. The study on Information seeking behaviour of Social Science Faculty was done by Chattwal (2014)² which indicates the pen-drive is most preferred as an external storage device due to its large storage capacity as well as convenience of usage was found to be the most preferred by 50.20% participants database appears to be the most suitable usage pattern for the University faculty members. Present study indicates that the main reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources are due to 'lack of awareness' by student non-users respondents. A similar study by Nikam & Pramodini (2007)³ indicates that reasons of non-use of UGC-INFONET resources by the Faculty Members and research scholars was 59.50% of respondents attributed the reason as lack of training/ orientation. The other reason included 28.50% of respondents attributed the reasons as 'lack of awareness' whereas 10.50% opted 'Aware but internet connection is not proper'. The authors concluded that the use was marginal and the scientist in the Mysore University Campus need constant guidance and training to maximise the use of UGC-INFONET e-resources. The similar study by Bhardwaj & Walia (2012)⁴ analyse the rating of the quality of the Electronic Resources in the St. Stephens College library, where majority of the respondents (52.8%) agreed that the 'Quality of the N-LIST e-resources are **excellent**' while 39.68% of the respondents rated the quality of the N-LIST e-resources were good. The authors also concluded that most of the respondents rated N-LIST e-resources very good. The similar study by Chikkanmanju and Kumbar (2015)⁵ identified the level of satisfaction of student respondents about the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources of the Tumkur University. The study reveals that 46.86% opined that the aided college students are extremely satisfied with the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources.

² Chattwal, A. (2014) Information Seeking Behaviour of Social Science Faculty: A Study of Universities of Punjab, Haryana and Chandigarh. (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis). Panjab University, Chandigarh (India).

³ Nikam, K & Pramodini, B. (2007). Use of E-Journals and Databases by the Academic Community of University of Mysore: A Survey. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*. 54, 1: 19-22.

⁴ Bhardwaj, R.K. & Walia, P. K.. (2012). Web Based Information Sources and Services: A Case Study of St. Stephen's College, University of Delhi. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. [http://www.webpages .uidaho.edu/~mbolin/ bhardwaj-walia.html](http://www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/bhardwaj-walia.html).

⁵ Chikkanmanju, & Kumbar, M. (2015) Use of Information Resources and Services by the Students of First Grade Colleges Affiliated to Tumkur University, Tumkur: A Comparative Study. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*. 3, 2: 53-64.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is an attempt to find out the accessibility of N-LIST E-resources and the usage trends used by the faculty and students of the Panjab University, Chandigarh.

The study was conducted with the following objectives:

- To analyze and compare the usage amongst the faculty and student users of the select Degree Colleges of Panjab University, Chandigarh.

HYPOTHESIS

Hypotheses H₀ 1 - There is no significant variation in the usage of e-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

H₁ 1 - There is significant variation in the usage of e-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

METHODOLOGY AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

A Survey method has been implemented to meet the objectives of the study. The author has collected the data through questionnaire method from the select Degree Colleges which are affiliated to Panjab University. The data have been collected from the 144 faculty users and 142 student users. In 144 faculty users, 114 are males and 30 are females whereas 142 student users, 33 are males and 109 are females. The statistical T-test has been applied to approve the null or alternate hypothesis. This method facilitates yearly accumulation of information from the member colleges in various settings under parameters relevant to the study.

SCOPE AND LOCALE OF THE STUDY

This study is confined to 18 member colleges. These member colleges are located in Punjab and Chandigarh and are affiliated to Panjab University only.

TIME PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The time period of the study will be from Jan 2010 to May 2015.

USAGE OF N-LIST E-RESOURCES

Hypotheses H₀ 1 - There is no significant difference in the usage of e-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

H₁ 1 - There is significant difference in the usage of e-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

Table 1: T-Test

Sr. No.	Variable	Faculty		Student		t-statistics	p-value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
	Frequency of Using N-list E-Resource	12.1597	1.67525	12.4014	1.52082	-1.278	.202
	Search strategy	10.5069	1.55098	11.1338	1.35390	-3.643	.000**
	Advance Search	15.0903	4.71705	17.0211	8.36954	-2.399	.017*
	Filter Result	10.2083	1.32683	10.6761	1.35033	-2.954	.003**
	Preferences of Resource type & Format	8.3403	1.58297	8.5704	1.88084	-1.119	.264
	Purpose of using N-LIST E-resources	24.2153	5.75874	27.1479	6.93429	-3.888	.000**
	Usage of E-Books	20.4375	3.63302	20.5775	4.99407	-.271	.787
	Usage of E-Journals	21.7361	4.66798	22.8592	5.86442	-1.790	.075
	Usage of Bibliographical E-resources	1.9583	.28665	1.8873	.46278	1.557	.121
	Usefulness of N-LIST E-resources	44.1319	7.98096	45.3239	10.73111	-1.065	.288
	Common Features	21.1667	11.21251	23.8310	12.01947	-1.938	.054
	Information Retrieved From N-LIST E-resources	11.3611	4.10970	11.7817	5.81892	-.705	.481
	Library Support for Users	11.1597	5.26456	9.1549	6.17395	2.953	.003**
	ICT Infrastructure for Users	15.8194	6.41529	14.3169	7.48082	1.822	.070
	Training Programmes for Users	15.3403	6.18951	14.2535	5.71850	1.543	.124
	External Storage Media while using N-LIST E-resources	12.5556	3.65616	10.4085	4.82334	4.238	.000**
	Problems in N-LIST E-Resources	27.4514	12.59805	31.5775	11.37580	-2.908	.004**
	Suggestions for access of N-LIST E-Resources Users	22.3194	9.11362	26.1197	8.94783	-3.558	.000**

From the above table, it has been analysed that:

1. Frequency of Using N-LIST E-Resources

The average values of Frequency of Using N-LIST E-resources for “faculty” and “student” are 12.16 and 12.40 with standard deviation 1.68 and 1.52, respectively. Since p-value for the N-LIST E-resources is .202 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the Frequency of Using N-LIST E-Resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

2. Search Strategy

The average values of search strategy for “faculty” and “student” are 10.51 and 11.13 with standard deviation 1.55 and 1.35, respectively. Since p-value for the search strategy is .000 which is less than 5% level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and there is a significant difference in the search strategy across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

3. Advance Search

The average values of advance search for “faculty” and “student” are 15.09 and 17.02 with standard deviation 9.71 and 8.37, respectively. Since p-value for the advance search is .017 which is less than 5% level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and there is a significant difference in the advance search across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

4. Filter Result

The average values of filter result for “faculty” and “student” are 10.21 and 10.68 with standard deviation 1.33 and 1.35, respectively. Since p-value for the filter result is .003 which is less than 5% level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and there is a significant difference in the filter result across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

5. Preferences of Resource Type and Format

The average values of resource type for “faculty” and “student” are 8.34 and 8.57 with standard deviation 1.58 and 1.88 respectively. Since p-value for the resource type is .264 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the preferences of resource type and format across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

6. Purpose of using N-LIST E-Resources

The average values of E-resource for “faculty” and “student” are 24.21 and 27.15 with standard deviation 5.76 and 6.93, respectively. Since p-value for the E-resources is .000 which is less than 5% level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and there is a significant difference in the purpose of using N-LIST E-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

7. Usage of E-Books

The average values of E-books for “faculty” and “student” are 20.44 and 20.58 with standard deviation 3.63 and 4.99, respectively. Since p-value for the E-books is .787 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the usage of E-books across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

8. Usage of E-journals

The average values of E-journals for “faculty” and “student” are 21.73 and 22.86 with standard deviation 4.67 and 5.86, respectively. Since p-value for the E-journals is .075 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the usage of E-journals across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

9. Usage of Bibliographical E-resources

The average values of bibliographical e-resources for “faculty” and “student” are 1.96 and 1.89 with standard deviation 0.29 and 0.46, respectively. Since p-value for the bibliographical e-resources is .121 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the usage of the bibliographical e-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

10. Usefulness of N-LIST E-resources (E-Books, E-Journals and Bibliographical Databases)

The average values of types of N-LIST E-resources for “faculty” and “student” are 44.13 and 45.32 with standard deviation 7.98 and 10.73, respectively. Since p-value for the types of N-list E-resources is .288 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the Usefulness of N-LIST E-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

11. Common Features

The average values of common features for “faculty” and “student” are 21.17 and 23.83 with standard deviation 11.21 and 12.02, respectively. Since p-value for the common features is .054 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the common features across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

12. Information Retrieved from N-LIST E-resources

The average values of information retrieved for “faculty” and “student” are 11.36 and 11.78 with standard deviation 4.10 and 5.82, respectively. Since p-value for the information retrieved is .481 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-

significant difference in the information retrieved across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

13. Library Support for Users

The average values of library support for “faculty” and “student” are 11.16 and 9.15 with standard deviation 5.26 and 6.17, respectively. Since p-value for the library support is .003 which is less than 5% level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and there is a significant difference in the library support across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

14. ICT Infrastructure for Users

The average values of ICT infrastructure for “faculty” and “student” are 15.82 and 14.32 with standard deviation 6.42 and 7.48, respectively. Since p-value for the ICT infrastructure is .070 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the ICT infrastructure across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

15. Training Programme for Users

The average values of training programme for “faculty” and “student” are 15.34 and 14.25 with standard deviation 6.19 and 5.72, respectively. Since p-value for the training programme is .124 which is more than 5% level of significance, hence it supports the null hypothesis and there is non-significant difference in the training programme across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

16. External Storage Media while using N-LIST E-resources

The average values of external storage for “faculty” and “student” are 12.56 and 10.41 with standard deviation 3.66 and 4.82, respectively. Since p-value for the external Storage is .000 which is less than 5% level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and that there is a significant difference in the external storage across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

17. Problems while using N-LIST E-resources

The average values of problems in N-LIST E-resources for “faculty” and “student” are 27.45 and 31.58 with standard deviation 12.59 and 11.38, respectively. Since p-value for the problems in N-LIST E-resources is .004 which is less than 5% level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and there is a significant difference in the problems in N-LIST E-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

18. Suggestions for access of N-LIST E-resources

The average values of access of N-LIST E-resources for “faculty” and “student” are 22.32 and 26.12 with standard deviation 9.11 and 8.95, respectively. Since p-value for the access of N-LIST E-resources is .000 which is less than 5%

level of significance, hence it contradicts the null hypothesis and there is a significant difference in suggestions for access of N-LIST E-resources across faculty members and student of the member colleges.

Findings from the T-Test (Variables showing Significant Difference)

The table below displays the variables showing significant Difference. The variables are as follows-

Table 2: Variables Showing Significant Difference

Sr. No.	Variable	t-statistics	p-value	Testing of Hypothesis
	Search strategy	-3.643	.000**	Null Hypothesis is rejected
	Advance Search	-2.399	.017*	Null Hypothesis is rejected
	Filter Result	-2.954	.003**	Null Hypothesis is rejected
	Purpose of using N-LIST E-resources	-3.888	.000**	Null Hypothesis is rejected
	Library Support	2.953	.003**	Null Hypothesis is rejected
	External Storage Media	4.238	.000**	Null Hypothesis is rejected
	Problems in N-LIST E-Resources	-2.908	.004**	Null Hypothesis is rejected
	Suggestions for access N-LIST E-Resources Users	-3.558	.000**	Null Hypothesis is rejected

Fig. 4.1

The above figure illustrates the t-statistics and p-value of the Search strategy, advance search, filter results, E-resources, library support, external storage, problem in N-LIST E-resources and Suggestions for access of N-LIST across faculty members and student of the member colleges. In this the highest t-statistics is 4.24 for external storage media which is significant at .000 (p-value) and the least t-statistics value is -3.89 for purpose of Using N-LIST E-resources which is significant at .000 (p-value). Since the p-value for these 8 variables is less than 5% level of significance. Hence, the Null Hypotheses for these variables are rejected and

alternate hypotheses are accepted in all the 8 concerning variables. Hence, it can be inferred that there is a significant difference among the above variables in the usage of N-LIST E-resources across faculty and student users.

Findings from the T-Test (Variables showing Non-Significant Difference)

The table below displays the variables showing non-significant Difference. The variables are as follows-

Table 3: Variables showing Non-Significant Difference

Sr. No.	Variable	t-statistics	p-value	Testing of Hypothesis
	Frequency of Using N-LIST E-Resource	-1.278	.202	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	Resource types	-1.119	.264	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	E-Books	-.271	.787	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	E-Journals	-1.790	.075	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	Bibliography	1.557	.121	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	Usefulness of N-LIST E-resources	-1.065	.288	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	Common Features	-1.938	.054	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	Information Retrieved	-.705	.481	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	ICT Infrastructure	1.822	.070	Null Hypothesis is Accepted
	Training Programmes	1.543	.124	Null Hypothesis is Accepted

Fig. 4.2

The above figure illustrates the t-statistics and p-value of N-LIST E-resources, research type, E-books, E-journals, bibliography, types of N-LIST E-resources, common features, information retrieved, ICT infrastructure and training programming across faculty members and student of the member colleges. In this the highest t-statistics is 1.82 for ICT infrastructure and the p-value for the same is 0.70 and the least t-statistics value is -1.79 for Usefulness of E-journals and the p-value for the same is 0.07 which is more than level of significance (5%). Since the p-value for these 10 variables is more than 5% level of significance. Hence, *the Null Hypotheses for these variables are accepted and alternate hypotheses are rejected in all the 10 concerning variables. Hence, it can be inferred that there is non-significant difference in the above variables in the usage of N-LIST E-resources across faculty and student users.*

Hence, the findings partially accepts the Null Hypothesis H_0 .

FINDINGS

- It has been noted that out of 18 variables 10 variables shows the non-significant difference while 8 variables shows significant difference in the usage of N-LIST E-resources across faculty and student users.
- It can be inferred that p-value of N-LIST E-resources, research type, E-books, E-journals, bibliography, types of N-LIST E-resources, common features, information retrieved, ICT infrastructure and training programming across faculty members and student of the member colleges are more than 5% level of significance, which

shows the non-significant difference in the usage of N-LIST E-resources across faculty and student users.

- It can be perceived that p-value of Search strategy, advance search, filter results, E-resources, library support, external storage, problem in N-LIST E-resources and Suggestions are less than 5% level of significance, which shows the significant difference in the usage of N-LIST E-resources across faculty and student users.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study at hand was focussed on the evaluation of usage of N-LIST E-resources in the Select Degree Colleges Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. The libraries should endeavour to launch a marketing plan to promote the usage of N-LIST E-resources and its awareness among the users through email alerts, text messages, social networking sites, whatsapp groups, blogs, and wikis etc. It is suggested that the subscription cost of N-LIST E-resources should be reduced to the same as earlier for the Non-aided colleges also.

Further the research in this regard will widen the criteria of the study and identify as to how the faculty and the student from the member colleges affiliated to other Universities explore the usage of the N-LIST E-resources. The authors feel that there is a need for appropriate and constant evaluation of this study in order to enhance insight into the usage analysis and the relevance of the information retrieved from the N-LIST E-resources.

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